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**TECHNICAL COMPETENCY NEEDS OF CARPENTRY AND JOINERY TRADE TEACHERS IN
GOVERNMENT SCIENCE AND TECHNICAL COLLEGES IN BAUCHI STATE NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to identify the technical competency needs of carpentry and joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State, Nigeria. Relevant research questions were formulated to guide the study. A survey research design was adopted, and the population comprised 39 respondents, including 21 management staff and 18 carpentry and joinery teachers in the selected colleges. Owing to the manageable size of the population, census technique was employed. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher and titled Technical Competency Needs of Carpentry and Joinery Teachers Questionnaire (TCNCJTQ). The reliability of the instrument was determined using Cronbach's Alpha, which yielded a coefficient of 0.85. The researcher administered the questionnaire to the respondents over a period of three weeks. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance using the t-test. All statistical analyses were conducted using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27.0. The findings revealed that carpentry and joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges needs 27 competencies related to carpentry and joinery. Based on these findings, it was recommended that the government should periodically evaluate teachers' competencies in obtainable at Technical Colleges level to determine their skill levels; the Ministry of Education should supply adequate raw materials to technical colleges to enhance teachers' capacity to develop frame construction skills; and the government should collaborate with industries to provide training for teachers on various types of carcass construction.

Keywords: Technical Competency, Carpentry, Joinery, Technical Colleges

INTRODUCTION

The primary objective of vocational and technical education is to equip learners with skills that promote self-reliance. It is a form of education designed to prepare individuals for gainful employment in occupations where success largely depends on technical knowledge and an understanding of scientific and technological principles as applied to modern design, production, distribution, and service delivery. Abdullahi et al. (2020) described vocational and technical education as outcome-driven, emphasizing its role in fostering technological advancement, supplying skilled manpower for employment, and providing continuing training for those already in the workforce to enable them adapt to modern work practices. Similarly, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN, 2019) defined vocational and technical education as aspects of education that, beyond general education, involve the study of technologies—particularly in technical colleges and related sciences—and the

acquisition of practical skills, attitudes, understanding, and knowledge relevant to occupations across various economic and social sectors.

According to Oviawe and Ehirheme (2020), technical colleges serve as the main vocational institutions in Nigeria, established to develop individuals with the practical skills, knowledge, and attitudes required for effective participation in the labour market. Salleh and Sulaiman (2020), as well as Inyiagu (2014), further noted that technical colleges provide training aimed at preparing students for entry into different occupational fields. The National Policy on Education according to Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN, 2019) highlighted the objectives of technical colleges to include preparation for productive living in society and readiness for further education. This implies that instruction in technical colleges should not only focus on developing learners' cognitive abilities but also emphasize the acquisition of relevant occupational skills, abilities, and competencies necessary for societal development. However, achieving the objectives of technical education, especially in trade-related courses, cannot rely solely on traditional "chalk and talk" methods; rather, it requires the effective utilization of instructional resources that actively engage students with the curriculum and practical learning activities. Okolie et al. (2021) defined educational resources as facilities available for achieving educational aims and objectives. Osuyi and Eboh (2020) also emphasized that quality human resources, particularly well-trained, qualified, and committed teachers, play a vital role in supporting students' development through practical projects and competency acquisition in woodwork-related services.

Carpentry and Joinery is among the vocational programmes offered in Nigerian technical colleges. Oviawe and Anaele (2020) explained that woodwork demands the acquisition of technical competencies for effective performance in trades such as frame construction, carcass construction, stool construction, and the proper use of tools and equipment during carpentry and joinery practical projects. Consequently, students enrolled in carpentry and joinery programmes must develop relevant competencies to enhance their employability in woodworking industries.

Competencies encompass the skills, knowledge, and attitudes that contribute to effective performance. Skills relate to the psychomotor domain, knowledge pertains to the cognitive domain, while attitudes reflect the affective domain necessary for successful task execution. Each learning outcome, referred to as a competency, is clearly defined and measurable. Azhari, Tze, and Endah (2021) described competency as the combination of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and judgment required for successful task performance, with judgment involving the application of cognitive and affective abilities in decision-making. Competencies can also be viewed as individual attributes or capabilities that determine effectiveness in the workplace. Shobowale et al. (2020) identified three main categories of competencies in vocational education programmes such as carpentry and joinery: basic, common, and core competencies. Despite this, the practical performance of technical college students in carpentry and joinery projects in Bauchi State is hindered by several challenges, including inadequate development of practical competencies by instructors, ineffective teaching methods, shortages of qualified teachers, insufficient facilities, and inadequate funding.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Technical colleges are established to produce skilled craftsmen who form the lower-level manpower required for national development. Students enrolled in technical colleges typically sit for an external examination conducted by the National Business and Technical Education Board (NABTEB). Graduates of these institutions are expected to acquire relevant practical skills that will enable them to become self-employed or gain paid employment in industries and other woodwork-related establishments.

Despite this expectation, many technical college graduates in Nigeria are not easily absorbed into industries due to inadequate practical skills required for executing real-life projects. Consequently, a large number of carpentry and joinery graduates leave school only to face unemployment. Unemployment remains one of Nigeria's most critical challenges, significantly hindering the country's economic growth. Furthermore, the performance of carpentry and joinery students in NABTEB practical examinations between 2016 and 2019 was generally poor, particularly in Bauchi State. According to the NABTEB Chief Examiner's report (2020), this unsatisfactory performance may be attributed to teachers' insufficient practical skills in key project areas such as frame construction, carcass construction, and stool construction. Other contributing factors include ineffective instructional methods, shortage of qualified carpentry and joinery teachers, inadequate facilities, and insufficient funding.

This situation has raised serious concerns among parents, industries, and other stakeholders regarding the poor performance of carpentry and joinery students in Bauchi State. As a result, there is a pressing need to identify the specific competencies required by carpentry and joinery teachers in technical colleges within the state.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The primary aim of this study was to identify the technical competency needs of carpentry and joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

- i. Identify the competencies currently possessed by carpentry and joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State.
- ii. Determine the competencies required by carpentry and joinery teachers in frame construction.
- iii. Determine the competencies required by carpentry and joinery teachers in carcass construction.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. What competencies are currently possessed by carpentry and joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State, Nigeria?
- ii. What competencies are required by carpentry and joinery teachers in frame construction?
- iii. What competencies are required by carpentry and joinery teachers in carcass construction?

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study was anchored on the Skill Development Theory proposed by Newell (1991). The theory explains that as learners acquire skills, observable changes occur in the strategies they use to achieve specific movement outcomes. Skill development involves learning how to control and coordinate posture, movement, and muscle activation to perform a wide range of motor activities within task constraints. Learners may demonstrate changes in body orientation, movement timing, and sequencing. This suggests that motor skill acquisition follows a progressive pattern that improves with consistent practice.

The acquisition of practical competencies is the core objective of technical college programmes. Education at this level is vocational in nature, with the primary aim of producing skilled workers rather than merely awarding certificates. Vocational education at the technical college level is designed to equip individuals with practical skills, scientific knowledge, and appropriate attitudes necessary for functioning as craftsmen and technicians at the sub-professional level (NGRF, 2018).

Achieving this objective depends largely on how responsive technical college programmes are to both students' employability needs and the competency expectations of prospective employers.

Frame construction, as defined by George (2009), refers to a building technique in which wooden components are organized around vertical structural members known as studs, forming a stable framework to which interior and exterior wall coverings are attached. When combined with horizontal ceiling joists and sloping rafters or prefabricated roof trusses, it is referred to as light-frame construction. Modern light-frame structures derive strength from rigid panels such as plywood and oriented strand board (OSB). Wall framing consists of vertical and horizontal components—including studs, wall plates, and lintels—that serve as nailing surfaces. The design of woodwork projects in frame construction is influenced by material selection, structure, shape, function, and aesthetics. When students understand these design principles, they can successfully carry out frame construction projects using basic skills such as measuring, cutting, and assembling timber components (Kumaran, 2003).

Carcass construction refers to woodworking projects with box-like structures. Walton (2001) described a carcass as the framework of a structure before it is covered with plywood or hardboard and before components such as drawers, doors, and shelves are installed. The objective of carcass construction is to develop learners' practical skills in using woodworking tools and producing basic joints and assemblies. It also enhances learners' understanding of woodworking materials, sustainability and recycling issues, and safe workshop practices.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design. According to Gall, Gall, and Borg (2007), a descriptive survey involves collecting data through questionnaires or interviews from a sample that represents a larger population, allowing the findings to be generalized. The study was conducted in Bauchi State, Nigeria, which lies between latitude 9.30°N and longitude 8.50°E of the Greenwich Meridian. Bauchi State shares boundaries with Gombe and Yobe States to the northeast, Plateau State to the southwest, and Jigawa and Kano States to the west.

The population of the study consisted of 39 respondents, including 21 management staff and 18 carpentry and joinery teachers from Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State. Due to the manageable size of the population, no sampling was carried out. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire developed by the researcher titled Technical Competency Needs of Carpentry and Joinery Teachers Questionnaire (TCNCJTQ). The instrument was structured in line with the research questions and divided into six sections (A–F). To establish reliability, a pilot test was conducted using carpentry and joinery teachers and school staff in Gombe State, which was not part of the study area. The Cronbach Alpha reliability method was employed, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.85.

The data collected were analyzed using appropriate statistical techniques. Mean statistics were used to answer the research questions, while t-tests were employed to test the null hypotheses at a specified level of significance. All analyses were conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 27. A cut-off mean score of 3.00 was used as the decision criterion for each item.

RESULTS

Research Question One

What competencies are currently possessed by carpentry and joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State, Nigeria?

This research question is answered by items in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Competencies Possessed by Teachers of Carpentry and joinery

S/No	ITEMS	N _M = 21		N _T = 18		N = 39		Remark
		\bar{x}	σ_M	\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_G	σ_G	
1.	Ability to assemble parts into finished products	4.19	0.51	4.06	0.24	4.13	0.41	Possessed
2.	Ability to apply finishers on projects	4.29	0.46	4.17	1.25	4.23	0.90	Possessed
3.	Ability to choose a particular finish on a project	4.43	0.75	4.17	0.71	4.31	0.73	Possessed
4.	Ability to cut wood project members to fit into each other	3.71	0.56	3.78	1.11	3.74	0.85	Possessed
5.	Ability to perform planning on the surfaces and edges of rough sawn timber	4.38	0.86	4.33	1.19	4.36	1.01	Possessed
6.	Ability to identify part members needed to be prepared by planning of faces /edges and cutting off ends	3.62	0.50	3.56	0.78	3.59	0.64	Possessed
7.	Ability to identify the shape /colour for a specific purpose	4.52	0.68	4.22	0.43	4.38	0.59	Possessed
8.	Ability to prepare specifications to give the desired size of a project	3.67	0.58	3.61	1.14	3.64	0.87	Possessed
9.	Ability to apply adhesive during assembling/finishing	1.90	0.83	1.67	0.49	1.79	0.70	Not Possessed
10.	Ability to maintain tools/ equipment in woodwork practice	4.29	0.64	3.89	0.96	4.10	0.82	Possessed
11.	Engaging in constant practical activities	4.29	0.56	4.22	0.65	4.26	0.59	Possessed
12.	Designing the project on drawing board	4.24	0.54	4.33	0.97	4.28	0.76	Possessed
13.	Selection of necessary materials	3.76	1.00	3.39	1.20	3.59	1.09	Possessed
14.	Forming of shaped parts	4.38	0.50	4.28	0.46	4.33	0.48	Possessed
15.	Finishing of the project to the expected standard	3.76	0.54	3.78	0.94	3.77	0.74	Possessed
16.	Test-trial of the project where applicable	4.48	0.51	4.44	0.51	4.46	0.51	Possessed
17.	The use of advance technology in classroom management	2.10	0.30	2.06	1.11	2.08	0.77	Not Possessed
18.	Engaging in practical project with students involved	4.62	0.50	4.33	0.84	4.49	0.68	Possessed
19.	The use of advance technology in teaching/learning	1.43	1.03	1.33	0.97	1.38	0.99	Not Possessed
20.	Ability to operate in a virtual environment	2.71	0.46	2.72	0.46	2.72	0.46	Not Possessed
21.	Selecting and applying appropriate tools for specific tasks	3.90	1.09	3.61	1.38	3.77	1.22	Possessed
22.	Ability to place tools in the right places	3.62	0.59	3.83	1.29	3.72	0.97	Possessed
23.	Ability to switch off electrical equipment when not in use	4.33	0.48	4.22	0.88	4.28	0.69	Possessed
24.	Ability to identify faulty machine	3.81	0.40	3.56	0.62	3.69	0.52	Possessed
25.	Ability to read signs of deformity in machines during work	3.67	0.66	3.61	0.70	3.64	0.67	Possessed
26.	Demonstrating proficiency in the	4.57	0.60	4.22	0.73	4.41	0.68	Possessed

	use of a vice							
27.	Ability to apply lubricant to wearing parts to avoid friction	3.48	0.68	3.17	1.04	3.33	0.87	Possessed
28.	Ability to store all planes in a rack designed to protect the cutting edges from damage/workers from injuries	4.10	0.54	3.72	0.57	3.92	0.58	Possessed
29.	Periodic safety inspections of infrequently used hand tools/machine	4.14	0.96	4.11	0.68	4.13	0.83	Possessed
30.	Ability to set up records to cover tool repairing/ replacement	3.38	0.67	3.11	0.32	3.26	0.55	Possessed
	Overall Mean	3.79		3.65		3.73		Possessed

\bar{x}_M = Mean of School Management Staff, \bar{x}_T = Mean of Teachers, σ_M = Standard deviation of School Management Staff, σ_T = Standard deviation of Teachers, \bar{x}_G = Grand Mean, σ_G = Grand Standard deviation, N_M = Number of School Management Staff, N_T = Number of Teachers, N = Total Number of Respondents

Table 1 presents the competencies possessed by Carpentry and Joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State. The results show that the respondents identified items 1–16, 18, and 21–30 as competencies possessed by the teachers, with mean values ranging from 3.59 to 4.49 and corresponding standard deviations between 0.51 and 1.09. However, the respondents indicated that the teachers did not possess the competencies listed in items 17, 19, and 20, which recorded mean values of 2.08, 1.38, and 2.37, and standard deviations of 0.77, 0.99, and 0.46 respectively. The overall mean score of 3.73 suggests that Carpentry and Joinery teachers generally possess most of the competencies required in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State.

Research Question Two

What competencies are required by carpentry and joinery teachers in frame construction? This research question is answered by items in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Competencies Needed in Frame Construction

S/No	ITEMS	$N_M = 21$		$N_T = 18$		$N = 39$		Remark
		\bar{x}	σ_M	\bar{x}_T	σ_T	\bar{x}_G	σ_G	
1.	Adopt correct and standard marks for a given project work	4.24	0.54	4.22	0.73	4.23	0.63	N
2.	Assemble the frame parts correctly without error	4.33	0.48	4.28	0.67	4.31	0.57	N
3.	Clean parts with modern sanders	4.43	0.60	4.44	0.51	4.44	0.55	N
4.	Complete the assembly of the project with appropriate framing joints	3.48	0.68	3.33	1.14	3.41	0.91	N
5.	Complete the project within a specified time limit	4.48	0.51	4.39	0.61	4.44	0.55	N
6.	Coordinates the constructional steps in the activities of frame construction in details	4.10	0.70	3.72	1.02	3.92	0.87	N
7.	Cut the bridle joints to the required shapes and sizes	2.95	0.67	2.89	0.68	2.92	0.66	NN
8.	Cut the frame members of the joints to suite the desired product	2.71	0.46	2.61	0.70	2.67	0.58	NN
9.	Design and make cutting list to guide the details of the frame	4.19	0.51	4.17	1.10	4.18	0.82	N

	construction							
10.	Draw vital frame joints	2.62	0.67	2.11	0.96	2.38	0.85	NN
11.	Interpret vital framing joints in construction	4.57	0.51	4.22	0.88	4.41	0.72	N
12.	Manipulate labour-saving manually operated machines to cut the mortise and tenon joints for frame construction	2.19	1.72	2.17	1.50	2.18	1.60	NN
13.	Operate power tools effectively for frame construction exercises	4.67	0.48	4.61	0.61	4.64	0.54	N
14.	Prepare pieces of wood members to the required length, widths and thickness for framing joints	4.57	0.60	4.33	0.97	4.46	0.79	N
15.	Set –up standard of proficiency to be met in frame construction of practical projects	3.86	1.15	3.33	0.84	3.62	1.04	N
16.	Set out the appropriate framing joints	1.95	0.22	1.72	1.13	1.85	0.78	NN
17.	Test the famed parts for flatness and squareness	3.62	0.59	3.50	0.86	3.56	0.72	N
18.	Applying technical knowledge and practical skills effectively in real workplace situations	4.24	0.83	4.22	0.81	4.23	0.81	N
19.	Trial test to assemble the pieces of frame members	3.81	0.40	3.67	0.49	3.74	0.44	N
20.	Use correct operational procedures in frame construction	3.76	0.62	3.50	0.79	3.64	0.71	N
	Overall Mean	3.74		3.57		3.66		Needed

\underline{x}_M = Mean of Management, \underline{x}_T = Mean of Teachers, σ_M = Standard deviation of Management, σ_T = Standard deviation of Teachers, \underline{x}_G = Grand Mean, σ_G = Grand Standard deviation, N_M = Number of Management, N_T = Number of Teachers, N = Total Number of Respondents, N = Needed, NN = Not Needed

Table 2 presents the competencies required in frame construction for Carpentry and Joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State, Nigeria. The findings reveal that respondents identified items 31–41, 43, 44, and 47–50 as necessary competencies, with mean scores ranging from 3.64 to 4.62 and corresponding standard deviations between 0.54 and 1.04. Conversely, items 37, 38, 40, 42, and 46 were rated as not required, as indicated by mean values of 2.18 and 1.85 and standard deviations of 1.60 and 0.78 respectively. The overall mean score of 3.66 suggests that Carpentry and Joinery teachers require 18 of the 21 listed frame construction competencies in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State.

Research Question Three

What competencies are required by carpentry and joinery teachers in carcass construction? This research question is answered by items in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation on the Competencies Needed in Carcass Construction

S/No	ITEMS	$N_M = 21$		$N_T = 18$		$N = 39$		Remark
		\bar{x}	σ_M	\underline{x}_T	σ_T	\underline{x}_G	σ_G	
1.	Assemble and secure the members with screws through the top rails	3.71	0.46	3.67	0.97	3.69	0.73	Needed
2.	Assemble the members temporarily for trial	4.57	0.51	4.50	0.51	4.54	0.51	Needed
3.	Attach ply or hard board sheeting	2.10	1.22	2.06	1.16	2.08	1.18	Not Needed

	over the carcass frames							
4.	Chop out waste of dovetail sockets and other mortises vertically and horizontally	3.57	0.60	3.72	1.36	3.64	1.01	Needed
5.	Chop out waste through from both sides	4.33	0.48	4.28	0.46	4.31	0.47	Needed
6.	Construct carcass from solid panels and join members permanently with special metal fasteners	4.00	0.77	3.83	0.62	3.92	0.70	Needed
7.	Construct carcass with suitable materials to meet the demand of the labour market	4.38	0.80	4.17	1.29	4.28	1.05	Needed
8.	Constructing mortise-and-tenon joints for cross rails, drawers, and shelving	3.52	0.68	3.56	1.15	3.54	0.91	Needed
9.	Construct the skeleton of the carcass structure	4.67	0.48	4.28	0.83	4.49	0.68	Needed
10.	Construct various forms of box or angle joints for solid end carcass	3.67	0.58	3.67	1.03	3.67	0.81	Needed
11.	Cut the narrow stiles or post and rails	4.48	0.75	4.28	0.46	4.38	0.63	Needed
12.	Establish functional projects that replicate industrial setting in carcass construction	2.38	0.74	2.33	0.77	2.36	0.74	Not Needed
13.	Execute and plant the top solid wood, multi-ply or particle board on top of the framework	4.29	0.46	3.94	0.87	4.13	0.70	Needed
14.	Gauge the positions of the joints across both sides and edges	4.24	0.70	4.39	0.50	4.31	0.61	Needed
15.	Join the carcass frame and test members for squareness	3.62	0.50	3.61	1.24	3.62	0.91	Needed
16.	Mark waste between dovetails and other joints with crosses	4.10	0.70	3.78	1.11	3.95	0.92	Needed
17.	Mark the shapes of pins and sockets and trace the shape of the gauged lines	4.62	0.50	4.11	0.96	4.38	0.78	Needed
18.	Prepare the carcass members to the required sizes of the pieces to be used for carcass construction	4.33	0.73	4.39	0.50	4.36	0.63	Needed
19.	Rip sides of dovetails and other joints members/sawing to the waste sides of the lines	4.19	0.60	3.83	1.15	4.03	0.90	Needed
20.	Rip the joints for top and bottom rails	2.14	0.48	2.11	0.76	2.13	0.61	Not Needed
21.	Set out the external faces of the joint members when they are to be seen	3.62	0.50	3.72	1.02	3.67	0.77	Needed
22.	Square the sides of the pins down to the gauge lines	4.29	0.64	4.44	0.51	4.36	0.58	Needed
23.	Use appropriate cutting/boring /driving tools in carcass construction	4.10	0.70	3.83	0.92	3.97	0.81	Needed
24.	Use flat fames for frame carcasses	2.38	0.74	2.33	0.69	2.36	0.71	Not Needed
	Overall Mean	3.80		3.70		3.76		Needed

\bar{x}_M = Mean of School Management Staff, \bar{x}_T = Mean of Teachers, σ_M = Standard deviation of School Management Staff, σ_T = Standard deviation of Teachers, \bar{x}_G = Grand Mean, σ_G = Grand Standard deviation, N_M = Number of School Management Staff, N_T = Number of Teachers, N = Total Number of Respondents

Table 3 presents the competencies required in carcass construction for Carpentry and Joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State, Nigeria. The results indicate that respondents identified items 51, 52, 54–61, 63–69, and 71–73 as essential competencies in carcass construction, with mean scores ranging from 3.54 to 4.54 and corresponding standard deviations between 0.51 and 1.18. In contrast, items 53, 62, 70, and 74 were considered not required, as they recorded mean values ranging from 2.08 to 2.36 and standard deviations between 0.61 and 1.18. The overall mean score of 3.76 suggests that Carpentry and Joinery teachers require most of the listed competencies in carcass construction in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This study out that the competencies by carpentry and joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges. Gives the overall mean score of 3.73 suggests that Carpentry and Joinery teachers generally possess most of the competencies required in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State. Vocational education at the technical college level is designed to equip individuals with practical skills, scientific knowledge, and appropriate attitudes necessary for functioning as craftsmen and technicians at the sub-professional level (NGRF, 2018). Achieving this objective depends largely on how responsive technical college programmes are to both students’ employability needs and the competency expectations of prospective employers.

This result found that the competencies that are required by carpentry and joinery teachers in frame construction. Indicate the mean score of 3.66 suggests that Carpentry and Joinery teachers require 18 of the 21 listed frame construction competencies in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State. Wall framing consists of vertical and horizontal components—including studs, wall plates, and lintels—that serve as nailing surfaces. The design of woodwork projects in frame construction is influenced by material selection, structure, shape, function, and aesthetics. When students understand these design principles, they can successfully carry out frame construction projects using basic skills such as measuring, cutting, and assembling timber components (Kumaran, 2003).

Furthermore, this result found out that the competencies that are required by carpentry and joinery teachers in carcass construction. With the overall mean score of 3.76 suggests that Carpentry and Joinery teachers require most of the listed competencies in carcass construction in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State. Carcass construction refers to woodworking projects with box-like structures. Walton (2001) described a carcass as the framework of a structure before it is covered with plywood or hardboard and before components such as drawers, doors, and shelves are installed. The objective of carcass construction is to develop learners’ practical skills in using woodworking tools and producing basic joints and assemblies. It also enhances learners’ understanding of woodworking materials, sustainability and recycling issues, and safe workshop practices.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings, it was concluded that Carpentry and Joinery teachers in Government Science and Technical Colleges in Bauchi State possess several essential competencies, including assembling parts into finished products, applying and selecting appropriate finishes, planning timber surfaces and edges, identifying suitable shapes and colours, maintaining

tools and equipment, designing projects on drawing boards, forming shaped parts, conducting test trials of projects, engaging students in practical work, observing safety practices such as switching off electrical equipment when not in use, securing materials properly during operations, applying lubricants to reduce friction, conducting periodic safety inspections, and maintaining records for tool repair and replacement. However, the teachers still require additional competencies in frame construction, carcass construction, stool construction, effective use of equipment, and proper maintenance of tools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- i. Government should regularly evaluate the competencies of Carpentry and Joinery teachers to determine their skill levels and training needs.
- ii. The Ministry of Education should supply adequate raw materials to technical colleges to enable teachers to effectively develop frame construction skills.
- iii. Government should collaborate with relevant industries to provide training opportunities for teachers on various types of carcass construction.

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